

SOAR: Semi-Automated Output Assessment and Review

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Semi-Automated Output Assessment and Review

SOAR Final Report

Executive Summary

The Semi-Automated Output Assessment and Review (SOAR) project evaluated the feasibility of using the TRevolution SACRO (Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs) tools within the Office for National Statistics (ONS) Secure Research Service (SRS). SACRO combines the ACRO analytical package, which performs automated Statistical Disclosure Checks (SDC) during analysis, with the SACRO Viewer, a structured interface for reviewing outputs.

Testing across three researcher cohorts demonstrated that SACRO has clear potential to enhance Trusted Research Environment (TRE) workflows. Researchers and output checkers highlighted several benefits, including earlier identification of disclosure risks, improved visibility of underlying statistical information, and a consistent, structured format for presenting outputs. These features indicate that semi-automated checking could, in the future, support more efficient and transparent SDC processes.

However, the project also identified significant limitations that currently prevent SACRO from being used operationally in a large TRE such as the SRS. These include gaps in statistical and modelling functionality, currently incomplete compatibility with common Stata and R workflows, and the need for more comprehensive TRE-specific guidance, which is particularly important given the offline nature of the SRS. As a result, SACRO is not yet ready for integration into SRS Business as Usual (BAU) processes.

The findings suggest that SACRO may be better suited at this stage to smaller TREs, where onboarding demands and user volumes are lower, and where iterative development in a live environment may be more manageable.

1. Introduction

1.1 The SOAR Project

The SOAR project was established to assess how semi-automated output checking could enhance the efficiency, scalability, and consistency of SDC within the SRS. Specifically, the project examined whether the SACRO toolkit could complement or partially automate elements of the SRS's existing SDC workflow, which currently relies on two independent manual checks.

1.2 The Secure Research Service

The SRS is one of the UK's leading TREs. TREs are secure digital platforms that allow accredited researchers to access de-identified or anonymised data while ensuring that sensitive information does not leave the controlled environment. All analysis is conducted within the TRE, and outputs can only be released after undergoing formal SDC checks. Operating under the Five Safes framework of Safe People, Safe Projects, Safe Settings, Safe Data, and Safe Outputs, the SRS supports over 100 high-quality datasets and processes more than 200 output requests each month. This scale places particular importance on efficient, robust, and transparent checking processes.

1.3 Project Aims

Assess the feasibility of using semi-automated output checking tools within the SRS.

SOAR sought to determine how effectively SACRO could be integrated into the existing SRS workflow, which currently relies on two independent manual SDC checks. This included examining the technical and operational considerations involved in embedding semi-automation into a highly regulated TRE environment.

Evaluate the tool's effectiveness in identifying disclosure risks.

SOAR aimed to compare the tool's performance with current manual checking processes to understand how well it detected SDC risks. This assessment included whether semi-automation could maintain or strengthen the high standards of security and compliance required for sensitive research outputs.

Explore researcher usability and remote access.

SOAR examined how researchers interact with the semi-automated tool directly, including whether remote access of SACRO within the SRS was feasible, user friendly, and secure.

Identify opportunities to operationalise the tool within BAU processes.

SOAR sought to understand workflow impacts, resource requirements, and potential efficiency gains, with the aim of outlining how the SACRO tool could be embedded into regular SDC checks. This supported wider thinking about TRE scalability and reducing pressure on manual output checker capacity.

1.4 The SACRO tools

SACRO, developed through the DARE UK TREvolution programme by the University of the West of England, consists of two key components:

- ACRO package: a Python based analytical library that runs automated SDC checks as researchers generate outputs, flagging potential risks (e.g., small counts, dominance) and providing structured results
- SACRO Viewer: a review interface that allows output checkers to inspect flagged outputs, view supporting metadata, log decisions, and maintain a consistent audit trail

Together, these tools provide a semi-automated approach to SDC, supporting researchers with early feedback while enabling output checkers to conduct more structured, consistent reviews.

1.5 Project Timelines

Phase 1 – Onboarding the Tools

The project began with onboarding the SACRO tools into the SRS environment. This required significant technical problem solving, as the complexity of the SRS infrastructure posed challenges. This was especially true when installing the Stata version of SACRO, which was critical given its use by around 70% of SRS researchers. Working closely with the tool's development team, these issues were resolved, enabling successful deployment of SACRO within the SRS. However, the time required to overcome these technical barriers caused delays early in the project, which in turn reduced the time available for researcher testing in later stages.

Phase 2 – Internal Testing and Preparation

After successful installation, the team conducted internal operability testing to ensure the tools behaved as expected. This included producing dummy outputs, reviewing them using the SACRO Viewer, and training output checkers on using it to ensure readiness for researcher facing testing. This phase confirmed that SACRO functioned within the SRS and that staff were sufficiently trained to use it.

Phase 3 – Researcher Testing

To ensure the SACRO tools were developed in a way that genuinely met the needs of researchers, we structured the testing across three separate researcher cohorts, running in December 2025, February 2026, and March 2026. This phased approach allowed us to gather learnings at the end of each cohort, identify any usability or functional issues, and feed these directly back to the SACRO team. By iterating in this way, insights from earlier cohorts informed adaptations and improvements ahead of subsequent testing windows, ensuring the product evolved in line with real researcher experience and supported a more robust and responsive development process.

Across these cohorts, participating researchers generated real analytical outputs within the SRS using SACRO. These outputs were then reviewed by output checkers using the SACRO Viewer. While the requests were not intended for export, because they formed part of the SACRO product testing, they still underwent the same process as standard SRS clearance requests. In total 41 researchers from 26 SRS research projects took part in the testing process.

Phase 4 – Researcher and Output Checker Feedback

During the testing windows, researchers were encouraged to produce a wide range of output types to assess how well SACRO handled varied analytical needs. Feedback was collected systematically at the point of output submission via a bespoke SACRO Output Request Form, ensuring accurate, real-time reflections on user experience. Researchers were also encouraged to share queries or suggestions to support tool refinement during weekly drop-in sessions. At the same time, output checkers provided insight into how SACRO assisted checking compared to existing manual processes, enabling evaluation of both efficiency and effectiveness.

1.6 Major outcomes and benefits

A primary benefit of the SOAR project was the development of a deeper understanding of where gaps currently exist in both the functionality and the guidance documentation of the SACRO tools. Through

structured testing across three researcher cohorts, the project was able to identify the practical requirements researchers have when working within a TRE, where internet access is not available, and where all analysis must be conducted using tools and resources that are fully contained within the secure environment. This insight was essential in highlighting aspects of SACRO that require refinement or clearer supporting guidance to ensure researchers can use the tools effectively in a constrained TRE setting.

Researchers participating in the testing windows provided detailed feedback on the functionality they needed SACRO to support to carry out their analysis. This included both missing features and improvements to existing ones, as well as aspects of the user workflow that needed to be more intuitive. All this feedback was systematically captured and shared with the SACRO product team, ensuring that it directly informed ongoing development work. As a result, the SOAR project not only evaluated SACRO's current capabilities but also played a key role in shaping its future direction, helping the tool evolve in line with the real-world needs of TRE researchers.

1.7 Why the project matters

The SOAR project is important because it provides real-world insight into how semi-automated SDC could operate in practice within a TRE. Rather than assessing SACRO in isolation, the project embedded the tools directly into day-to-day SRS workflows and observed how researchers and output checkers interact with them. This practical, hands-on testing allowed us to evaluate the current readiness of SACRO to support or replace certain elements of manual checking and to identify where the technology performs well, where gaps exist, and what adaptations would be required for safe and effective use.

By trialling SACRO across multiple researcher cohorts, SOAR demonstrated how semi-automation could potentially support efficiency, consistency, and risk reduction. However, it also highlighted the further development needed before SACRO could be considered for BAU integration, including enhancements to functionality, clearer guidance documentation, and improvements to usability to ensure researchers can use the tools effectively in a TRE without internet access. Ultimately, the project matters because it moves the conversation from theoretical possibilities to evidence-based understanding, providing the foundation for informed decisions about how semi-automated output checking could be adopted safely, responsibly, and at scale within TREs such as the SRS.

2. Feedback on SACRO

2.1 Utility of SACRO for Trusted Research Environments

Feasibility testing showed that the SACRO toolkit, comprising the ACRO automated checking library and the SACRO Viewer, offers several tangible benefits for TREs seeking to enhance the efficiency, consistency, and governance of SDC. While further development is required before large scale operational use, particularly in a TRE as complex as the SRS, researcher and output checker feedback highlighted several clear utilities.

2.1.1 Benefits of the ACRO Package

Researcher testing showed that the ACRO package has value as an early-stage quality assurance tool for researchers.

2.1.1.1 Rapid sense checking of outputs before submission

Researchers reported that ACRO is effective for quickly identifying which outputs are safe, borderline, or clearly unsuitable for release. This allows researchers to triage their own outputs before initiating an output request, reducing burden on output checkers further down the line.

2.1.1.2 Effective identification of dominance risks

A notable finding from testing was ACRO's strong performance in identifying dominance issues, instances where a small number of records heavily influence an output. These risks are often challenging to detect through manual checks alone yet represent an important category of SDC concern. Researcher feedback highlighted that ACRO's automated dominance checks were both reliable and easy to interpret.

2.1.1.3 Live feedback embedded within analysis workflows

Because ACRO runs checks at the point of output creation, researchers receive immediate alerts about potential SDC issues. Researchers indicated that live feedback is likely to reduce:

- The number of disclosive outputs requested
- The volume of blocked output requests
- Time spent iterating with output checkers
- Overall burden on manual SDC processes

It should be noted that this project's testing environment may have encouraged more cautious researcher behaviour than typical SRS conditions. Nonetheless, researcher feedback suggests that integrating ACRO into standard workflows would reduce disclosive submissions and improve TRE efficiency.

2.1.2 Benefits of the SACRO Viewer

Output checkers highlighted several advantages of the SACRO Viewer for supporting structured and consistent review processes.

2.1.2.1 Consistency and clarity in output formatting

Output checkers emphasised that the SACRO Viewer improved clarity and standardisation across outputs. Because ACRO exports follow consistent structural conventions, the SACRO Viewer ensures:

- Uniform presentation of statistical outputs
- Clear identification of flagged values
- Easier comparison between outputs and across projects

By ensuring that outputs are presented in a consistent format, this is likely to reduce the burden on output checkers who would otherwise need to assess material with wide variation in structure, style, and presentation. This consistency also strengthens the reproducibility of decisions around SDC risk, as output checkers can apply the same criteria to outputs that are formatted in a comparable way.

2.1.2.2 *Improved visibility of underpinning statistical information*

Output checkers highlighted that the SACRO Viewer makes key underpinning information, such as counts, residual degrees of freedom, and other SDC relevant indicators, immediately visible. This directly addresses two common challenges in manual output review:

- Outputs submitted without necessary counts
- Outputs submitted where data cannot easily be cross referenced to underlying counts

By removing ambiguity around these elements, the SACRO Viewer reduces the need for reviewer follow-up, reducing burden on TREs and unnecessary delays for researchers.

2.1.2.3 *Structured, auditable interface for release decisions*

Output checkers also commented on the SACRO Viewer's structured interface, and the potential this has in strengthening governance and auditability. Use of the SACRO Viewer provides:

- Clear logging of output checkers actions
- Structured comment and exception fields
- A consistent audit trail

This creates a robust and transparent audit trail, which is particularly valuable for TREs operating across multiple requests.

2.1.2.4 *Summary of identified SACRO benefits*

Across both ACRO and the SACRO Viewer, SACRO offers meaningful utilities for TREs. This includes earlier detection of SDC risks, improved researcher self-checking of their outputs, more structured review processes, and greater consistency in decision making. While further operational testing is required, user feedback indicates strong potential for SACRO to support semi-automated SDC.

2.2 Current limitations of SACRO and Recommendations for Improvement

Testing also identified limitations that would need to be addressed before SACRO could be used effectively in larger TREs. These relate to technical capability, workflow compatibility, and the availability of sufficient guidance and onboarding materials.

2.2.1 Current Technical Limitations

2.2.1.1 Limited Support for Complex Statistical Designs

Researchers reported that SACRO currently struggles with analytical workflows requiring complex sampling structures. Researchers stated missing features included:

- Non-response weighting
- Stratification parameters
- Svysset-based workflows
- Clustered standard errors

These methods are common in SRS research, and without support for them, ACRO cannot reliably assess SDC risks for many analyses. Extending SACRO's handling of weights, clusters, and survey structures would significantly improve its applicability.

2.2.1.2 Gaps in Regression and Modelling Functionality

Researcher feedback highlighted that SACRO still falls short of supporting the full range of modelling methods necessary for work carried out within the SRS. Researchers highlighted missing elements including:

- Stata factor variable notation (i.var)
- Stata if qualifiers within regression commands
- Modified Poisson regression with robust errors in R
- Hierarchical and multi-level models
- Clustered model structures
- Extended survival analysis workflows (e.g., group comparisons, model extensions)

These gaps restrict SACRO's current use within the SRS, particularly given the wide range of methodological needs across topics including health, education, labour markets, justice and economics. Without broader syntax support and additional modelling tools, SACRO cannot fully meet the analytical requirements of many SRS users.

2.2.1.3 Lack of Automated Rounding of Counts

Researchers identified that SACRO does not currently have an option to apply automated rounding of counts, which is a mandatory SDC requirement for some SRS datasets. Researchers noted that without built-in rounding, outputs will not be suitable for export from the SRS, limiting its suitability for researchers using those datasets.

Currently missing features include:

- Automatic rounding of cell counts
- Dataset-specific rounding rules
- System checks in SACRO Viewer to identify unrounded counts

Introducing a consistent, configurable rounding mechanism would ensure SACRO meets data owner requirements and supports safe release of outputs for these datasets.

2.2.1.4 Workflow Compatibility and Integration Issues

Both R and Stata users experienced workflow friction when integrating SACRO into their usual analytical processes. Compatibility gaps affecting workflows included:

- Limited support for tidyverse/dplyr pipelines (including tibble compatibility)
- Lack of Stata if qualifiers and factor variables

- Limited visualisation options (e.g., no histograms)

These issues make adoption more difficult in offline TRE environments where researchers cannot troubleshoot via the internet.

2.2.2 Guidance, Documentation, and User Support Needs

While Stata documentation was expanded significantly during the project, researchers continued to report gaps, particularly when dealing with more complex or edge case scenarios. Documentation for R remained particularly limited, largely due to project time constraints, and this created challenges for researchers using R who required more structured, language specific guidance.

Researchers highlighted several key areas where documentation and onboarding materials remain insufficient:

- Limited onboarding materials tailored to R environments, including guidance on typical R workflows
- Limited R specific examples and worked workflow templates
- Unclear expectations around unsupported features, TRE-specific constraints, and how SACRO behaves in an offline environment

Because TRE researchers typically have restricted time with data and no access to online resources, these documentation gaps slow progress and reduce confidence in the semi-automated checking process. Strengthening guidance would better support researcher self-sufficiency and reduce the need for troubleshooting during analysis.

To meet researcher needs, the documentation would benefit from:

- Expanded materials for R and Stata, including more complex worked examples, troubleshooting guides and end-to-end workflow demonstrations
- Clear lists of supported and unsupported syntax and modelling functions
- More user-friendly onboarding formats, including further development of video walkthroughs and interactive tutorials, to help researchers understand SACRO more quickly within TRE constraints

2.2.3 Summary of current SACRO limitations

Researchers considered SACRO highly promising but noted key areas requiring development. The most significant challenges relate to:

- Support for complex survey methods and clustering
- Gaps in modelling and regression functionality
- Lack of automated rounding
- Workflow compatibility issues with tidyverse and core Stata features
- Uneven and incomplete documentation and user guidance

Addressing these limitations, particularly those involving complex designs, hierarchical data, workflow integration, and improved user onboarding will be essential to scale SACRO effectively across larger TRE environments such as the SRS.

2.3 Potential Benefits from Integrating SACRO into Daily BAU Practice

Introducing SACRO into routine TRE workflows has the potential to enhance efficiency, governance, and user experience. While the tool is still developing and not yet ready for full-scale deployment, findings from feasibility testing indicate several areas where SACRO could meaningfully strengthen SDC processes.

2.3.1 Streamlined workflows and stronger governance

Embedding ACRO within analysis would enable researchers to identify issues earlier, reducing unnecessary iteration. The SACRO Viewer provides a consistent review interface that strengthens auditability and supports reproducible SDC decisions. Together, they reinforce a clear two-stage workflow aligned with the Four Eyes Principle, a governance and assurance practice that requires two independent output checkers to review, approve, or verify an output before it can be approved for clearance from a TRE.

2.3.2 Enhancements to Data Quality, Security, and Efficiency

By identifying risks such as dominance and small counts during analysis, SACRO can reduce the volume of high-risk outputs submitted for review. Automated checks enable more efficient triage and support scalable SDC capacity in TREs experiencing high output volumes.

2.3.3 Increased Organisational Capacity and Improved Communication

Even modest reductions in disclosive submissions can free capacity for output checking teams, allowing them to focus on analytically or conceptually complex cases. SACRO's standardised formatting can also improve communication between researchers and reviewers, providing a shared basis for understanding why outputs are flagged and how to address them.

2.3.4 Improvements in User Experience

SACRO offers researchers clearer, more predictable feedback through live risk indicators. This reduces the reliance on back-and-forth correspondence with output checkers and helps researchers understand SDC requirements during their analysis. The SACRO Viewer presents outputs in a consistent, accessible format that has the potential to reduce the burden on output checkers.

2.3.5 Broader Sector and Community Benefits

Wider adoption of tools like SACRO could support greater standardisation of SDC practices across TREs, improving predictability for researchers and enhancing overall SDC quality. Enhancing transparency and ensuring consistent decision-making can play a key role in strengthening public trust in TRE operations. As demand for TRE access grows, SACRO represents an important step toward more scalable, technology supported SDC capacity.

3. Feedback on the Adoption Process

3.1 Challenges Encountered

3.1.1 Technical Challenges During Onboarding

Early internal testing identified significant onboarding issues, particularly in ensuring the ACRO package functioned correctly for Stata users, a critical requirement given that around 70% of SRS researchers use Stata. These issues stemmed from incompatibilities between SACRO and existing SRS infrastructure and required close collaboration between SRS and the SACRO development team to diagnose and resolve. Although the problems were ultimately addressed, they caused delays and highlighted the need for clearer, TRE-specific installation guidance.

3.1.2 Practical Challenges Reported by Researchers

Once researcher testing began, further challenges emerged due to gaps in user facing documentation. Because researchers operate without internet access in the SRS, the available guidance proved insufficiently detailed, particularly for the earlier testing cohorts. Researchers struggled to understand SACRO workflows and how to apply the ACRO package in practice. These issues were identified through direct feedback to the SOAR team and led to improvements in the documentation. However, time constraints meant that additional refinement will still be required for future adoption.

3.2 Recommendations for Improving the Adoption Process

Several improvements would support a smoother and more efficient adoption process in future TRE environments:

- **Strengthened researcher guidance:** including a clear workflow overview, step-by-step instructions, and further TRE accessible supplementary materials such as offline tutorials or examples
- **Clearer installation documentation for TRE operators:** covering setup steps, expected configuration issues, and guidance on supporting researchers through the SACRO workflow
- **Greater clarity on SACRO's current capabilities and limitations:** enabling TREs to assess suitability and set realistic expectations before onboarding begins

Collectively, these enhancements would reduce onboarding delays, improve user confidence, and ensure TREs can better plan for SACRO's integration.

3.3 Lessons Learned

3.3.1 What went well

The phased cohort structure enabled iterative learning, with feedback from early cohorts directly informing improvements in later testing. Collaboration between SRS teams and SACRO developers was constructive and responsive, allowing issues to be escalated quickly and resolved where possible. SRS researchers also engaged proactively with the project, contributing valuable insight into practical needs and workflow requirements.

3.3.2 Unexpected insights

A key insight was the extent to which researchers depend on workflow compatibility, particularly around Stata syntax, tidyverse patterns, and statistical modelling. Even minor incompatibilities had disproportionate impacts within an offline TRE environment. Additionally, the early maturity of SACRO shifted the project's focus from assessing capability to supporting product development. SACRO's current limitations meant that empirical assessment of its SDC-checking performance compared to manual checks was not feasible. Instead, the experience underscored how essential a robust baseline of functionality and documentation is before tools can be evaluated for effectiveness in TRE workflows.

3.3.3 Lessons Learned and Advice for Future Adopters

The challenges encountered offer several key lessons:

- Integrated, comprehensive guidance should be developed early to support researcher testing
- Tool maturity must be communicated clearly to manage expectations and avoid misalignment between intended and actual capability
- Iterative testing cycles are valuable, particularly for early-stage tools
- Adequate support capacity is essential, as early adoption requires substantial troubleshooting and user assistance

The experience highlights the importance of aligning expectations between product developers and TRE operators, ensuring products are sufficiently mature before large TREs are able to adopt them, and providing structured onboarding resources for tools intended for use in complex environments like the SRS.

3.4 Future Use of SACRO

While SACRO demonstrates long term potential, its current maturity and the scale of SRS operations mean it is not yet suitable for routine use. The SRS processes more than 200 output requests per month and requires tools that are fully stable, well documented, and compatible with a wide range of analytical workflows. At present, SACRO would require extensive onboarding support and troubleshooting capacity that cannot be accommodated alongside BAU pressures.

In the short term, SACRO is likely to be more viable in smaller TREs, where adoption is more manageable and can continue to inform tool development. Future evaluation within the SRS may be appropriate once SACRO's functionality, stability, and TRE-specific documentation have matured.

3.5 Support Needed for Continued or Expanded Use

Continued involvement by the SRS in SACRO's development would require:

- Sustained funding to support staff time, maintain service delivery, and enable meaningful collaboration with the SACRO team
- Ongoing technical support from SACRO to extend functionality, improve workflow compatibility, and ensure stability within offline environments

- Expanded documentation and training materials, ensuring researchers and output checkers can use the tool confidently and effectively

These elements would allow the SRS to maintain high quality service for researchers while contributing constructively to SACRO's continued evolution.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.